

PROCEEDINGS

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Exploring patterns of breast cancer tumor characteristics using factor analysis

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Abstract

Breast cancer is one of the significant global health challenges, demanding a deeper understanding of its complex nature for improved diagnosis and treatment. This study sought to identify the underlying factors in breast cancer tumor characteristics using the factor analysis technique. The dataset which comprised of 7 tumor characteristics measurements of 569 patients was sourced from kaggle.com, <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/yasserh/breast-cancer-dataset>. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity were employed to justify the factor analysis assumptions thereby ensuring the suitability of the dataset for factor analysis. The principal component technique was used to estimate the factor loadings and communalities while the varimax rotation technique was employed in the interpretation of these latent factors. The result of the analysis showed that the first two components accounted for 81.7% of the total variance and that while the first component captured a set of variables related to tumor size (radius mean, perimeter mean, and area mean), the second component was associated with characteristics related to tumor shape (smoothness mean, compactness mean, and concavity mean). The identified patterns are recommended for improved diagnostic methods and tailored treatment approaches in the fight against breast cancer.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Tumor Characteristics, Factor Analysis, Principal Component, Varimax Rotation, Latent Factors.

Introduction

Breast cancer is a health challenge characterized by the uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells within the breast tissue. Breast cancer ranks as the most frequently diagnosed cancer among women and holds the top spot as the most prevalent cancer worldwide. The year 2020 witnessed over 2.26 million new instances of breast cancer in women. It is the leading cause of cancer-related deaths globally, making it a critical public health concern. Breast cancer can affect individuals of all genders, although it is most commonly associated with women (World Cancer Research Fund International, 2022).

Tumors form when a single cell divides unchecked, leading to an unwelcome growth known as cancer. Breast cancer symptoms include an increase in breast mass, a change in breast size and form, a change in breast skin color, breast discomfort, and changes in the breast's genetic makeup. Worldwide, breast cancer has been described to be the second leading cause of death in women after heart disease and it affects more than 8% of women at some point in their lives. According to the WHO's annual report, more than 500,000 women have breast cancer every year. It is predicted that the prevalence of this disease will arise in the future due to environmental damage (World Health Organization Annual Report, 2015).

Obesity, hormone treatment therapy during menopause, family medical history of breast cancer, lack of physical activity, long-term exposure to infrared energy, having children later in life or not at all, and early age at which first menstruation occurs, race and ethnicity, being taller, some birth control methods and drinking alcohol/smoking are some of the risk factors for breast cancer in women. (Shaikh, *et al* 2021)

Many tests, including ultrasound, biopsy, and mammography, are performed on patients to determine whether they have breast cancer. This is because the symptoms of breast cancer vary widely. The biopsy, which includes the extraction of tissue or cell samples for analysis, is the most suggestive of these procedures. Humankind has struggled to understand and treat breast cancer since the earliest documentation more than 3500 years ago. The visible signs and symptoms of breast cancer and the palpability and tangibility of the lumps at later stages of the disease have enabled easy diagnosis by physicians in almost every period of recorded history. Tumor characteristics play a pivotal role in the prognosis, treatment planning, and personalized medicine for breast cancer patients.

Factor analysis is a multivariate technique designed to analyze correlations among many observed variables and to explore latent factors. Factor analysis was developed by the British statistician and psychologist Charles Spearman in the early 20th century as a technique for analyzing intelligence structure. Factor analysis plays a crucial role in data analysis and interpretation for several reasons: It simplifies complex datasets by reducing the number of variables while retaining essential information. This simplification makes data more manageable and interpretable. Factor analysis reveals hidden patterns and associations among variables that may not be apparent through direct observation. It uncovers the underlying structure that drives observed correlations. It groups related variables under common factors, providing a more comprehensive view of the data. This grouping helps researchers focus on broader constructs and simplifies subsequent analysis. Factor analysis enhances the interpretability of data by identifying the key factors that explain its variance. This understanding aids in making informed decisions and drawing meaningful conclusions (Tavakol & Wetzel, 2020).

Factor analysis has found applications in various fields, including psychology, social sciences, environmental sciences, machine learning, finance, medicine and health care, education, marketing, biostatistics and genetics, human resources, engineering, and more.

In studying diseases, Luo *et al.* (2020) applied factor analysis in the study of the clinical symptoms of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) based on a combination of factors. Factor loadings were calculated, and pairwise correlation analysis of symptoms was performed and the result of the investigation showed that the clinical symptoms of COVID-19 cases could be divided into respiratory-digestive, neurological, cough-wheezing, upper respiratory, and digestive symptoms.

Wu, *et al.* (2020) applied factor analysis in the investigation of the relationship between the gut microbiome and breast cancer risk factors and tumor characteristics. In their pilot cross-sectional study involving 37 incident breast cancer patients, they analyzed fecal samples collected before chemotherapy using a 16S ribosomal RNA gene-based sequencing protocol. Statistical analyses such as the Wilcoxon rank-sum test and a zero-inflated negative binomial regression model were employed, adjusting for total counts, age, and race/ethnicity. However, their work rightly acknowledged the need for further investigations to comprehensively understand the characteristics of the human microbiome and its intricate interplay with breast cancer hormone receptor status and established risk factors.

This study aims to identify underlining factors and relationships in breast cancer tumor characteristics by applying factor analysis to a set of seven key variables. Although there are numerous breast cancer tumor characteristics, this work restricts itself to seven of them, namely; radius mean, texture mean, area mean, perimeter mean, smoothness mean, compactness mean, and concavity mean. These variables derived from breast cancer cell images are commonly used in diagnostic processes, and hold crucial information about the nature and behavior of the tumor.

1. Methodology

2.1 Data and Data Preparation

The dataset which comprised of 7 tumor characteristics measurements of 569 patients was sourced from kaggle.com, <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/yasserh/breast-cancer-dataset>. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity were used to verify that the dataset satisfied the assumption for Factor. Descriptive statistics were generated for the seven (7) variables using the SPSS software.

2.2 Factor Analysis Model

Factor analysis which is basically a one-sample procedure for possible applications to data with groups was used in the analysis. Assume a random sample y_1, y_2, \dots, y_p from a homogeneous population with mean vector μ and covariance matrix Σ . The factor analysis model expresses each variable as a linear combination of underlying factors f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m with an accompanying error term to account for that part of the variable that is unique (not in common with the other variables). For y_1, y_2, \dots, y_p in any observation vector y , the model is presented in equation 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_1 - \mu_1 &= \lambda_{11}f_1 + \lambda_{12}f_2 + \dots + \lambda_{1m}f_m + \varepsilon_1 \\
 y_2 - \mu_2 &= \lambda_{21}f_1 + \lambda_{22}f_2 + \dots + \lambda_{2m}f_m + \varepsilon_2 \\
 &\vdots \\
 y_p - \mu_p &= \lambda_{p1}f_1 + \lambda_{p2}f_2 + \dots + \lambda_{pm}f_m + \varepsilon_p \dots \dots \dots (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where:

y 's are the random variables

μ 's are called mean vectors

f 's are called latent factors

λ_{ij} 's are called loadings

ε 's are the residuals

Model (1) can be written in matrix notation as:

$$y - \mu = \Lambda f + \varepsilon \quad \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

$$y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_p)'$$

$$\mu = (\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_p)'$$

$$f = (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m)'$$

$$\varepsilon = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_p)'$$

$$\Lambda = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{11} & \lambda_{12} & \dots & \lambda_{1m} \\ \lambda_{21} & \lambda_{22} & \dots & \lambda_{2m} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \lambda_{p1} & \lambda_{p2} & \dots & \lambda_{pm} \end{pmatrix} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

The aim is to find f 's from y 's such that m is substantially smaller than p ($m < p$). Before fitting the model, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity were employed to justify the factor analysis model assumptions after which the factor loading (λ_{ij}) were estimated using the principal component method which were used describe each extracted factor component. The varimax rotation, a widely used technique in factor analysis which serves in enhancing the interpretability of latent factors was used to streamline the understanding of how specific tumor attributes align with underlying factors.

2. Results and Discussion

3.1 Data Presentation

The data for this work is secondary data consisting of breast cancer tumor characteristics from kaggle.com <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/yasserh/breast-cancer-dataset>. The dataset comprises 569 subjects each with seven (7) distinct breast cancer tumor characteristics. The tumor characteristics include: radius mean (average size of the tumor's radius), texture mean (mean value of the grayscale levels in the tumor's texture), perimeter mean (mean perimeter of the tumor), area mean (mean area covered by the tumor), smoothness mean (mean smoothness of the tumor's boundaries), compactness mean (mean compactness of the tumor, $\text{perimeter}^2 / \text{area} - 1.0$), and concavity mean (mean level of concavity within the tumor). The data is presented in Appendix 1

3.2 Justification of Factor Analysis Assumption.

The result of the KMO and Bartlett spherical test is presented in Table 1. The KMO value of 0.719 which lies within the range of 0.7 to 0.8 indicating that the degree of information among the variables overlaps greatly. Hence factor analysis can be conducted on the dataset.

This is further justified by Bartlett's test of sphericity with a highly significant p-value (sig. = 0.00), indicating a significant relationship between the variables in the dataset. This is a positive outcome because factor analysis assumes that variables are related.

TABLE 1
KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity for Breast Cancer Tumor

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.719
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	8086.053
	Df	21
	Sig.	<.001

3.3 Descriptive statistics

The result of the descriptive statistics of the variables is presented in Table 2. From the result, it can be observed that the columns display the number of data points (N), range, minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, and variance. The radius mean contains 569 data points with a range of 21.1290, varying from a minimum of 6.9810 to a maximum of 28.1100. The mean radius is approximately 14.13, with a standard deviation of 3.52, indicating the spread of data around the mean. The variance, at 12.42, quantifies the degree of dispersion within the dataset.

The statistics for other features are similarly presented, offering insights into the characteristics of the dataset. The area mean has a much larger variance compared to the other features, suggesting greater variability in the data points. Additionally, some features like smoothness mean exhibit very small standard deviations, indicating that the data points are clustered closely around the mean.

TABLE 2
Descriptive Statistics of the Breast Cancer Tumor Characteristics

Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Radius mean	569	21.1290	6.9810	28.1100	14.127	3.524	12.419
Texture mean	569	29.5700	9.7100	39.2800	19.290	4.301	18.499
Perimeter mean	569	144.7100	43.7900	188.5000	91.969	24.2989810	590.440

Area mean	569	2357.500 0	143.5000	2501.0000	654.889	351.914	123843.554
Smoothness mean	569	.1108	.0526	.1634	.096360	.0140641	.000
Compactness mean	569	.3260	.0194	.3454	.104341	.0528128	.003
Concavity mean	569	.4268	.0000	.4268	.088799	.0797198	.006
Valid N (listwise)	569						

3.4 Factor Analysis Using Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix of the dataset is presented in Table 3. The correlation matrix shows how variables in the analysis correlate with each other. Rows and columns correspond to different variables, while the values reflect the strength and direction of their linear relationship. For "radius mean" and "texture mean," the correlation is 0.324, suggesting a weak positive relationship between these variables. Similarly, high positive correlations are observed between "radius mean" and "perimeter mean" (0.998), "radius mean" and "area mean" (0.987), "perimeter mean" and "area mean" (0.987), "compactness" and "concavity mean" (0.883), indicating strong positive relationships between these variables. The "Sig. (1-tailed)" section provides p-values indicating the significance of the correlations. In this case, most of the correlations have extremely low p-values (typically < 0.001), suggesting that the observed correlations are statistically significant.

Table 4 shows the communalities of the variables. The initial communality of radius mean is 1.000 indicating that the variability in the variable is initially attributed to the variable itself. However, after conducting the factor analysis (using Principal Component Analysis), the extraction communality is 0.952. This suggests that the extracted factors explain 95.2% of the variance in radius mean, and the remaining variance (4.8%) is not captured by the factors. For texture mean, the extraction communality is 0.262 indicating that the extracted factors explain 26.2% of the variance in the variable while the remaining variance (73.8%) is not captured by the factors.

The total variance explained by the components is presented in Table 5. The result reveals that two (2) factors were extracted with a cumulative percentage of 81.748. The remaining five factors have lower cumulative loadings and minimal variation. Therefore, their contribution to the total variance is relatively small to be considered less important in this analysis, this result is further collaborated by the Scree plot presented in Figure 1.

TABLE 3
Correlation Matrix of Tumor Characteristics

Correlation Matrix a								
		radius mean	texture mean	perimeter mean	area mean	smoothness mean	compactness mean	concavity mean
Correlation	radius	1.000	0.324	0.998	0.987	0.171	0.506	0.677

	mean							
	texture mean	0.324	1.000	0.330	0.321	-0.023	0.237	0.302
	perimeter mean	0.998	0.330	1.000	0.987	0.207	0.557	0.716
	area mean	0.987	0.321	0.987	1.000	0.177	0.499	0.686
	smoothness mean	0.171	-0.023	0.207	0.177	1.000	0.659	0.522
	compactness mean	0.506	0.237	0.557	0.499	0.659	1.000	0.883
	concavity mean	0.677	0.302	0.716	0.686	0.522	0.883	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	radius mean		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	texture mean	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.289	0.000	0.000
	perimeter mean	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	area mean	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
	smoothness mean	0.000	0.289	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000
	compactness mean	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000
	concavity mean	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
a. Determinant = 6.063E-7								

TABLE 4
Communalities of the Breast Cancer Tumor Characteristics

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
radius mean	1.000	0.952
texture mean	1.000	0.262
perimeter mean	1.000	0.963
area mean	1.000	0.946

smoothness mean	1.000	0.842
compactness mean	1.000	0.883
concavity mean	1.000	0.875
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

TABLE 5
 Total Variance Explained by the Components

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.328	61.822	61.822	4.328	61.822	61.822	3.371	48.152	48.152
2	1.395	19.926	81.748	1.395	19.926	81.748	2.352	33.596	81.748
3	0.850	12.136	93.885						
4	0.327	4.672	98.557						
5	0.086	1.234	99.791						
6	0.014	0.205	99.996						
7	0.000	0.004	100.000						
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.									

FIG1: Scree Plot of Breast Cancer Tumor Characteristics

3.8 Factor Loading

The factor loading is presented in Table 6, from where it can clearly be seen that tumor perimeter mean has a strong positive loading (0.937) on the first component and a negative loading (-0.292) on the second component. Similarly, tumor radius mean has a high positive loading (0.915) on the first component and a negative loading (-0.338) on the second component and so on. From the analysis with $p = 7$ and $m = 2$, the resulting factor model is given as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_1 - \mu_1 &= 0.945f_1 + 0.245f_2 + \varepsilon_1 \\
 y_2 - \mu_2 &= 0.940f_1 + 0.249f_2 + \varepsilon_2 \\
 y_3 - \mu_3 &= 0.936f_1 + 0.296f_2 + \varepsilon_3 \\
 y_4 - \mu_4 &= 0.511f_1 + \varepsilon_4 \\
 y_5 - \mu_5 &= 0.913f_2 + \varepsilon_5 \\
 y_6 - \mu_6 &= 0.352f_1 + 0.872f_2 + \varepsilon_6 \\
 y_7 - \mu_7 &= 0.571f_1 + 0.741f_2 + \varepsilon_7
 \end{aligned}$$

where, $y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_7$ are the radius, texture, perimeter, area, smoothness, compactness, and concavity means respectively and f_1 and f_2 are respectively the tumor size tumor shape.

The rotated component matrix provided in Table 6 applies varimax rotation method to simplify the loadings and enhance interpretability.

Factor 1

Variables such as radius mean, perimeter mean, and area mean, have strong positive loadings (around 0.9), indicating that they are highly positively associated with Component 1. This

suggests that these variables tend to vary together, and their values contribute significantly to the variability explained by Component 1. Variables such as compactness mean and smoothness mean on the other hand have very low to no loading on Component 1, which suggests a weak relationship. Furthermore, tumor texture mean and concavity mean have moderate positive loadings on Component 1, indicating that even though they contribute to Component 1, the extent of the contribution is low compared to the variables with high positive loadings.

Factor 2

The Varimax rotation also indicate that tumor smoothness mean, compactness mean and concavity mean have strong positive loadings on Component 2 indicating their high positive association with Component 2. Tumor radius mean, area mean, and perimeter mean on the other hand have relatively weak positive loadings on Component 2.

In general, these results provide insights into the underlying structure of the data. Component 1 seems to capture a set of variables related to tumor size (radius, perimeter, and area), while Component 2 appears to be associated with characteristics related to tumor shape (smoothness mean, compactness mean, and concavity mean).

TABLE 6
Component Matrix and Rotated Component Matrix for Tumor Characteristics

Component Matrix a			Rotated Component Matrix a		
	Component			Component	
	1	2		1	2
perimeter mean	0.937	-0.292	radius mean	0.945	0.245
radius mean	0.915	-0.338	area mean	0.940	0.249
area mean	0.914	-0.333	perimeter mean	0.936	0.296
concavity mean	0.892	0.282	texture mean	0.511	
compactness mean	0.787	0.514	smoothness mean		0.913
texture mean	0.404	-0.315	compactness mean	0.352	0.872
smoothness mean	0.447	0.801	concavity mean	0.571	0.741
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
a. 2 components extracted.			Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.		
			a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.		

3.9 Component Transformation Matrix

The component transformation matrix is presented in Table 7. The value 0.821 in the first row, first column (1, 1) indicates that the first initial component has a strong positive relationship with the first rotated component. The value 0.571 in the first row, second column (1, 2) shows that the first initial component also has a moderate positive relationship with the second rotated component. Similarly, the value -.571 in the second row, first column (2, 1) demonstrates that the second initial component has a moderate negative relationship with the first rotated component. The value .821 in the second row, second column (2, 2) suggests that the second initial component has a strong positive relationship with the second rotated component.

Varimax rotation with Kaiser normalization has been applied to enhance the clarity of the loadings structure, making it easier to comprehend the relationships between components and variables.

TABLE 7
 Component Transformation Matrix for Tumor Characteristics

Component Transformation Matrix		
Component	1	2
1	0.821	0.571
2	-0.571	0.821
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.		

3. Conclusion

In exploring patterns of breast cancer tumor characteristics namely radius mean, texture mean, perimeter mean, area mean, smoothness mean, compactness mean, and concavity mean using factor analysis, two major underlying factors that are involved in describing tumor characteristics based. The first component captured a set of variables related to tumor size namely radius mean, perimeter mean, and area mean while the second component is associated with characteristics related to tumor shape namely smoothness mean, compactness mean, and concavity mean.

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